

IMPACT OF FREE INSECTICIDE-TREATED NET POLICY ON MALARIA BURDEN AMONG CHILDREN IN ORON LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study assessed the impact of the free insecticide-treated net policy on the burden of malaria among children in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Malaria according to WHO is considered a leading cause of child mortality globally and the Nigerian experience in particular. Children under five years of age are most susceptible to malaria infection because of their developing immune systems and inability to produce sufficient antibodies to fight Plasmodium parasites. The study adopted the health belief model as the theoretical framework. The model noted that attitudes and beliefs of individuals affect their preferences and utilisation of medical services, and this is particularly useful in understanding the impact of health intervention policies such as the free Insecticide Treated Net and how various factors determine the effectiveness of the policy. The study adopted a multi-sampling technique and a questionnaire was used for the collection of data on Likert Scale. Data were analysed descriptively from the Likert scale. The findings of the study indicated that malaria significantly impacts children's health and development resulting in stunted growth, diminished cognitive function more detrimental educational achievement and could mortality. The study further identified numerous risk factors, such as climatic conditions, location and malaria vectors, socio-economic determinants and effectiveness of control strategies which amount to a high malaria burden among children in the study area. The study noted that the use of a malaria-treated net would reduce the burden of malaria on young children and therefore recommended more awareness of the need to utilise the strategy and thus reduce the burden of malaria transmission on children. The study also recommended government, non-governmental, and community leaders' partnership in encouraging the use of insecticide-treated nets for children by parents and caregivers for protection against malaria transmission.

Keywords: Malaria, Children, Free Insecticide-Treated Net, and Policy

Introduction

Malaria is an enormous health challenge affecting humanity with young children being the most affected globally. Malaria disease is caused by the Plasmodium parasite and

transmitted by mosquito vector, known as *Anopheles gambiae*. It is a life threatening disease and remains one of the most dangerous parasitic infections that plague humans health and their socio-economic wellbeing WHO (2023) reported that more than 3 billion people live in regions that are considered susceptible to malaria infection, and 50 per cent of the world's population; indicating an annual mortality record which ranges from one million to three million globally die of malaria (World malaria report, 2020). According to the Global Technical Strategy for Malaria 2016-2030 (2016), approximately 90 per cent of the world's burden of malaria is in Africa, Asia and South America. In these regions, malaria transmission and infection remain high, with young children as groups that are especially vulnerable to the effects of malaria (Uneke, 2018).

Data from Roll Back Malaria Partnership Campaign (2016) revealed that malaria threatens 3.2 billion lives people globally with a serious impact on vulnerable children, killing an estimated 1 to 2 million yearly and causing illness in about 300 to 500 million people. Africa is a malaria-endemic region where approximately 25 million women become pregnant annually and are at risk of *Plasmodium Falciparum* infection during pregnancy (WHO, 2022). These factors according to Curtis, Jana-Kara, and Maxwell (2003) contribute to the high rate of maternal and neonatal morbidity/mortality in Africa. Studies by WHO (2016) revealed that Nigeria is one of the hardest hit by malaria in Sub-Saharan Africa, where the disease accounts for 11 per cent of maternal mortality and 12 to 30 per cent of mortality as well as its complicated effects on children. The severity of malaria is worsened by pregnancy as a result of distinct malarial parasites that bind to the placental (White, 2008). The prevalence of parasitaemia appears greatest in the second trimester and susceptibility to clinical malaria may persist into the early postpartum period.

However, despite progress in reducing malaria incidence and mortality rates over the past decade, young children remain particularly vulnerable due to their developing immune systems. The consequences of malaria in children under five are severe and multi-dimensional. It impacts the children's health, development, and well-being. According to White (2008), one of the most common complications of malaria in young children is severe anaemia. Infecting and also destroying the red blood cells, leads to a significant reduction in haemoglobin levels. Severe anaemia causes fatigue, weakness, and pallor that can lead to heart failure in extreme cases. Chronic anaemia in children under five can impair the progress of their physical and cognitive development, thus affecting their growth and ability to learn.

In addition, malaria can lead to Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS), a severe condition characterized by rapid onset of widespread inflammation in the lungs. Children with ARDS experience severe difficulty in breathing, which can lead to hypoxia (low oxygen levels in the blood). ARDS requires immediate medical intervention and is associated with high mortality rates. Survivors of ARDS may suffer from long-term respiratory issues (Darteh, Baubeng, Akuamoah-Boateing (2019).

Studies by Aluko and Oluwatosin (2012) revealed that malaria remains the leading cause of maternal, child and infant morbidity and mortality in Nigeria and upon this, the free Insecticide Treated Net Policy program was initiated to reduce the burden of malaria, promote evidence-based and cost-effective control interventions. The free Insecticide Treated Net Policy is the overall national strategy adopted to combat malaria and its burden on human health especially among children. The ITN strategy seeks to establish a social movement in which local communities, public and private sectors, all tiers of government

and non-governmental agencies come together in partnership and network to initiate and implement malaria control activities (Aluko and Oluwatosin, 2012). The four key intervention strategies of ITN, which is recommended by WHO are: case management of malaria during pregnancy, using Sulfadoxine/pyrimethamine (SP) as a drug of choice for intermittent preventive treatment (IPT), widespread use of Insecticide Treated Nets (TiNs) and antenatal care (ANC) (Aluko and Oluwatosin, 2012). ITNs are promising tools to combat malaria in the country among children which are also beneficial to women during pregnancy, particularly in malaria-endemic areas where environmental sanitation has become a serious problem beyond individual manageable capacity and where there is stagnant water.

Determined to accelerate and intensify efforts on malaria control in Nigeria, the Federal Government through the Federal Ministry of Health, National Malaria Control Programme, and in partnership with the ITN partners, as well as States' Ministries of Health and their Local Government Areas, with other stakeholders, have collaborated to enable a national scale-up of key preventive and curative interventions. They designed and developed a five-year National Malaria Strategic Plan (NMSP) to prevent and control the burden of malaria. Of this, the ITN goals and the MDGs were targeted for 2010 and 2015, respectively (Udom and Udousoro, 2024). Moreover, given government's strategy to control malaria using ITN programme, limited studies have been conducted to assess the relationship between ITN and the social status of beneficiaries. Thus, in light of the above, this study examines the impact of the free Insecticide Treated Net (ITN) policy in reducing the burden of malaria among children under five in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to assess the impact of free insecticide-treated net (ITN) policy in reducing the burden of malaria among children. Specifically, the study:

- i. to assess the effectiveness of the free ITN policy in reducing malaria incidence among children under five in Nigeria.
- ii. to identify the barriers faced by households in utilizing insecticide-treated nets provided under the free ITN policy.

Literature Review

Insecticide-treated net (ITN) is a cost-effective vector control and preventive approach for malaria and transmission which has become a burden in society, especially in the malaria-endemic areas (WHO, 2001). Mosquito insecticides known as insecticide-treated nets (ITNS) or bed nets - were developed in the 1980s for malaria prevention and control. A fact sheet from the World Health Organization has been cited that ITNs are estimated to be twice as effective as untreated nets (WHO, 2001). It has been revealed that the prevalence of malaria in pregnancy is highest in first-time pregnancies and in women aged 15-19 years, (Udom and Udousoro 2024) decreasing with subsequent pregnancies as well as HIV-infected women regardless of the number of previous pregnancies (Desai, Nosten, McGready, Asamoah and Bradbin, 2007). The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends universal coverage with long-lasting insecticide-treated nets (LLINs) for the prevention of malaria in pregnancy and among children under 5.

Insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) are considered the mainstay of Malaria prevention and as a vector control intervention, they are effective in preventing maternal morbidity and mortality in

a range of epidemiological settings. In reducing the densities and infectivity of malaria vectors, they reduce overall transmission and protect all individuals within a community (WHO, 2006). Mosquito nets have been advocated by the Federal Ministry of Health, WHO and other health partners as the most preventive tools against malaria especially in sub-Saharan Africa. Insecticide-treated bed nets are seen as a powerful tool to reduce malaria transmission at the community level, representing the first line of defense against the disease. Insecticide treated bed nets have played an important role in the remarkable success towards reducing malaria burden and enhancing the socio-economic well-being of beneficiaries. The World Health Organization recommends that universal coverage and access to, as well as use of insecticide bed nets remains the goal for all beneficiaries at risk of malaria and that this should be achieved through mass, free distributions, and continuous distributions through multiple partners and channels by both public and private sectors.

The evidence for the efficacy of ITNs in preventing malaria infection and its consequences in pregnancy is strong, as reported in a Cochrane review in 2009. and a more recent meta-analysis (Eisele, Laisen, Anglewicz, Keating, Yukich, Bennett, Hutchinson and Steketee, 2012), which examined malaria prevention in pregnancy datasets from different African nations indicated that the use of treated nets has reduced transmission of malaria. The evidence showed a strong correlation between the use of ITNs and a reduction in stillbirths, improvements in birth weights of babies and a reduction in the prevalence of parasitaemia and anaemia among beneficiaries. A communal protective effect of ITNs and a reduction in overall vector density have also been observed in some settings (Kilicen *et al.* 2007). Malaria in pregnancy is a major public health problem. It contributes to severe anaemia in the mother and low birth weight for babies, which are associated with poor infant health and early infant death. Also, the unborn child and the pregnant woman may die from malaria during pregnancy (Curtis Jana-kara Maxwell, 2003), and to avert this, protection with insecticide-treated bed nets (ITNs) during pregnancy is widely recommended. An insecticide-treated net (ITN) is a net (usually a bed net), designed to block mosquitoes physically, that has been treated with safe, residual insecticide to kill and repel mosquitoes, which carry malaria from transmitting malaria to man.

Bisi-Onyemaechi, Obianu, Chikani, Ogonna and Ayuk (2017) in a study of the determinants of the insecticide-treated net (ITN) use among caregivers of under-five children in Enugu, Southeast Nigeria revealed that the educational status of caregivers was the most significant factor influencing ITN use ($P=0.001$) in the area, indicating that beneficiaries social status; their level of education and awareness have away or influences their usage of and choice of medical services (Willie, Udom and Mboho, 2024).

Ukibe, Mban ugo, Obiokoro and Ukibe (2014) in their study to assess knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of beneficiaries concerning the use of insecticide-treated bed nets (ITNs) in Anambra State, South-East Nigeria showed that out of 700 respondents, 651 (93 per cent) knew about ITNs, 420 (60 per cent) owned nets out of which 235 (56 per cent) refused to use ITNs. The reasons for refusal to use ITNs were as follows: excessive heat (40.3 per cent), inadequate accommodation to hang nets (13.3 per cent), house was netted (11.7 per cent), ITNs do not work (3.7 per cent), het caused itching (0.7 per cent), heard ITNs killed someone (1.7 per cent), does not like ITNs (4 per cent), no reason at all (24 per cent). The study concludes that whereas the women's knowledge about ITNs was good, their attitudes and practices were health barriers, recommending education and mass literacy campaigns to

address the challenge.

Yitayw, Wnyew and Goshu (2018) in a study of the utilization and associated factors of insecticide-treated nets among beneficiaries in Adis Zemen Hospital were more likely to utilize insecticide-treated bed nets than mothers who could not read and write as well as Mothers whose age were >30 than mothers whose age were 30 and less. Studies by Udom and Udousoro (2024), and Udom and Peters (2024) indicate that education and awareness of medical services have a way of influencing their utilization by beneficiaries. However, utilization and perception of treated net by beneficiaries is low in the rural area basically because of their level of awareness to the benefit of ITNs. The participants' age, educational status, household, monthly income, and husband's educational status were significantly associated with perceptions that influence the utilization of medical services (Victor and Udom, 2023) including the use of insecticide-treated bed nets.

Some researchers have noted that women who used ITNs had significantly fewer preterm deliveries and babies with higher mean birth weight than women who did not use ITNs. Nevertheless, the use of ITNs is still limited mainly because of their unavailability and cost, and partly because of the discomfort associated with the nets and the women's fear of the possible effects of the impregnated chemicals on them and their unborn babies (Mbonye, Neema and Magnusen, 2006).

Good governance according has been identified as another means through which access to service could be made possible to beneficiaries. The authors noted that the government should create an awareness campaign team to educate the people on the benefits of utilizing the services as well as subsidizing the costs since a major factor determining the use of ITN among these beneficiaries is cost and knowledge of causative organisms. It shows that local knowledge of causative organisms is highly relevant to the social marketing strategies of TTNs. The Uptake of ITN can be significantly improved in low-income areas if the cost of the nets is subsidized and affordable for the beneficiaries and as well backed up with appropriate health education intervention by the government.

Ezeama, Ezeameh and Akor (2014) in examining factors militating against the utilization of insecticide-treated nets by beneficiaries noted that the majority were aware of the insecticide-treated net but usage was low. Most respondents reported experiencing excessive heat under the net and thus were afraid of the chemicals used in producing the net and suffocation. Level of education, marital status and parity were also highly associated with the use of ITNs. Findings suggest that intensive public enlightenment campaigns by the government and other agencies were necessary to dispel the fear of chemicals used in treating the ITNs and heat produced by ITNs to encourage use among beneficiaries. Other factors identified include low utilization of antenatal care, husband's lack of interest in malaria prevention and perceptions that adolescent girls are at low risk of getting malaria. The implications of these findings include demystifying the negative perceptions of the chemicals used for net treatment and subsidizing the cost of ITNs to increase access.

According to WHO (2006), Insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) have been recommended as the main malaria control and prevention strategy. This is due to their effectiveness in preventing maternal morbidity and mortality in a range of epidemiological settings, as they reduce the densities and infectivity of malaria vectors, thus reducing transmission among individuals within a community. To ensure equality of access, WHO, (2016) recommended

that ITNs be provided free of charge for all especially those at risk (universal coverage): this is to be coupled with effective behaviour change communication by the government to increase usage and proper maintenance. Mosquito nets have thus been advocated for as the most preventive tools against malaria.

Theoretical Framework

Health Belief Model

The Health Belief Model (HBM) was propounded by Hochbaum. Rosentock and Kegels (1950) are adopted as the framework for this study. The model helps to explain and predict health behaviours by focusing on the attitudes and beliefs of individuals in their preference and utilization of medical services. The model is particularly useful in understanding the impact of health interventions, such as the free Insecticide Treated Net (ITN) policy in Nigeria, aimed at reducing malaria among children under five. The HBM consists of several key components namely: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and self-efficacy. This model analyzes how health behaviours influence the utilization of ITN policy and outcomes in vulnerable populations.

The beneficiary's belief can enhance perceived susceptibility which can be overcome through increasing awareness among parents and caregivers on the burden of malaria attack on children of five.

Educational campaigns accompanying the ITN distribution emphasize that young children are particularly vulnerable to malaria due to their developing immune systems and their usage of ITN determined by caregivers and percent perception of ITN. When caregivers understand that their children are at high risk of contracting malaria and its burden, they may be more motivated to use ITNs consistently. The policy's educational components highlight severe health outcomes of malaria, including anaemia, cerebral malaria, and even death, which are particularly dangerous for young children. By reinforcing the serious nature of malaria, the policy increases the perceived severity of the disease among caregivers, encouraging them to prioritize preventive measures like ITN use and environmental sanitation. The free ITN policy directly addresses perceived benefits by donating ITNs to the people, demonstrating their effectiveness in preventing mosquito bites and malaria transmission. Information campaigns shared will influence the health beliefs of caregivers influencing their attitudes to the use of ITN to reduce the transmission of malaria burden in society. When caregivers recognize the clear benefits of ITNs in protecting their children from malaria, they are more likely to use them consistently.

The Health Belief Model analyzes how various psychological factors influence the perception and belief of the caregivers and how it further affects the effectiveness of the policy in reducing malaria among children under five. By reducing perceived susceptibility and severity, through emphasis on the benefits of ITNs. Addressing barriers, providing cues to action, and boosting self-efficacy, could be achieved through an integrated health belief which will help improve the perceptual and utilization of health facilities that will address the burden and barriers experienced by beneficiaries, especially the children. This, the beneficiaries will significantly improve their ITN utilization and, consequently, reduce the burden of malaria.

Methodology

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design because it guarantees its strength in generating accurate data from research participants at a relatively friendly financial cost. The study was conducted in Oron Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State because of its swampy nature with an environment habitat environment for mosquito breeding.

Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in the selection of all research elements. The technique entails the use of multiple sampling techniques such as simple random, purposive and systematic stratified sampling technique. The questionnaire was adapted as the main instrument for data collection. The Cochran sample determinant was adopted in determining the sample size. To determine the sample size for this study, Cochran's formula (1963) was adopted. The formula for the Cochran sample size determinant is stated thus:

$$n = \frac{Z^2(pd)}{e^2}$$

Where:

- n = Required sample size
- Z = Confidence level (put at 95% or 1.96)
- p = Proportion of respondents (given in this study as 50%). That is 0.5
- q = Compliment of p (put at 50%, i.e. 1 - 50%). That is 0.5
- e = Level of accuracy or margin error (put at 0.05).

Applying the formula therefore,

$$n = \frac{1.96^2(0.5)(0.5)}{0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416(0.25)}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 384.16$$

$$n = 384$$

Result

Out of three hundred and eighty-four (384) questionnaires administered, three hundred and fifty-eight (358) were recovered and used for analysis. Results of the analysis of demographic data of respondents revealed that out of the 358 accessible respondents', 241 respondents representing 67.31% were females, while 117 representing 32.68% were males. As for age distribution of respondents', 71(19.83) are below 20 years, 111(31.00) are between 30-39 years, 146 (40.78) are between 40-49 years, 30(8.37) are 50 years and above. For respondents' marital status, 137 (38.26) are single, 155(43.29) are married, 28 (7.82) are divorced, 22(6.14) are widows, 16(4.46) are widowers. For respondents' educational qualification; 27(7.54) have FSLC, 61 (17.03) have secondary SSCE, 82 (22.90) have OND/NCE, 168 (46.92) have HND/BSC and 20(5.58) have M.Ed/Ph.D.

Analysis of research objectives

Objective one

i. To assess the effectiveness of free ITN policy in reducing malaria infection and transmission among children in Oron Local Government Area.

Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) were used to respond to the research objective. Participants' responses are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Responses on the effectiveness of the free ITN policy in reducing malaria infection and transmission among children

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD
1	I am aware of the free ITN policy.	186 (51.95)	118 (32.96)	37 (10.33)	17 (4.74)
2	I have children under the age of five in my household.	210 (58.65)	106 (29.60)	23 (7.82)	14 (3.91)
3	I have received an ITN through the free ITN policy.	167 (46.84)	101 (28.21)	61 (17.03)	29 (8.10)
4	I received enough ITNs for all children under five in my household	205 (57.26)	123 (34.35)	18 (5.02)	12 (3.35)
5	There were no challenges in receiving ITNs from the distribution centre.	191 (53.35)	114 (31.84)	38 (10.61)	15 (4.18)
6.	The ITN is currently being used in my household	155 (43.29)	162 (45.25)	18 (5.02)	23 (6.42)
7.	My Children under five slept under an ITN last night	168 (46.92)	121 (33.79)	41 (11.45)	28 (7.82)
8.	I believe that ITNs are effective in preventing malaria	178 (49.72)	110 (30.79)	41 (11.45)	28 (7.82)
9.	Since receiving the ITN, I have noticed a reduction in malaria cases among my children under five	199 (55.58)	81 (22.62)	53 (14.80)	25 (6.98)
10.	The health of my children under five has improved since using the ITN	222 (62.01)	78 (21.78)	38 (10.61)	20 (5.53)

Source: Field survey, 2024

Objective two

ii. Identify the barriers faced by households in utilizing insecticide-treated nets provided

under the free ITN policy.

Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) were used to respond to the research objective. Participants' responses are presented in Table 11

Table 2: Responses on the barriers faced by households in utilizing insecticide-treated nets provided under the free ITN policy

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD
1	I find it difficult to hang the ITN properly in my home.	24 (6.70)	20 (5.58)	196 (54.74)	118 (32.96)
2	The sleeping arrangements in my home make it hard to use the ITN	215 (60.05)	91 (25.41)	41 (11.45)	11 (3.07)
3	There is enough space in my home to hang the ITN correctly.	199 (55.58)	116 (32.40)	28 (7.82)	15 (4.18)
4	The cost of obtaining ITNs is a barrier for my household	202 (56.42)	120 (33.51)	27 (7.54)	9 (2.54)
5	I can afford the necessary repairs or replacements for the ITNs	166 (46.36)	128 (35.75)	42 (11.73)	22 (6.14)
6.	I believe that ITNs cause discomfort when sleeping	218 (60)	122 (34.07)	8 (2.23)	10 (2.79)
7.	My Children under five slept under an ITN last night	168 (46.92)	121 (33.79)	41 (11.45)	28 (7.82)

Source: Field survey, 2024

Discussion of Findings

The study findings of objective one show that the free ITN policy is effective in reducing malaria infection among children in the study area. The effectiveness of the Free Insecticide-Treated Net (JTN) policy in reducing malaria disease among children has been a significant focus of malaria control efforts. Various empirical studies have demonstrated the positive impact of ITNs in preventing malaria transmission and improving health outcomes for this vulnerable population. Eisele *et al.* (2010) conducted a comprehensive review of the protective efficacy of ITNs in preventing malaria disease among children in Plasmodium falciparum endemic areas. The study agreed with the findings that ITNs significantly reduced malaria-specific mortality by 55% among children under five. This evidence strongly supports the effectiveness of ITNs in reducing malaria incidence and improving survival rates in young children. Yusuf *et al.* (2008) findings also agreed with the fact that the cost-effectiveness of ITNs in preventing malaria in sub-Saharan Africa will enhance usage by beneficiaries. The study demonstrated that ITNs are not only effective in reducing malaria incidence but also cost-effective as compared to other means of treatment, making them a viable intervention for large-scale implementation. The findings showed that ITNs could avert approximately 50% of malaria cases among children under five, supporting their

widespread use in malaria-endemic areas like Oron in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Noor *et al.*, (2009) assessed the temporal trends in malaria transmission following the scale-up of ITN distribution in Kenya. The study found that widespread ITN use led to significant reductions in malaria transmission and clinical malaria cases. These results are consistent with the observed impact of the free ITN policy in Nigeria, where similar distribution efforts have contributed to reduced malaria incidence among young children.

The findings of the second objective show barriers faced by households in utilizing insecticide-treated nets provided under the free ITN policy. Beer *et al.*, (2012) explored the factors influencing ITN usage in malaria-endemic regions like that of the study area. The findings identified barriers such as lack of awareness, cultural beliefs, and improper ITN usage. However, it also emphasized the role of community engagement in education in overcoming these barriers. The findings suggest that the free ITN policy, coupled with effective community education, can enhance ITN utilization and reduce malaria infection among children. The study found that targeted distribution, continuous education, and follow-up visits were critical in ensuring ITN effectiveness. The study findings revealed that the strategies when implemented in partnership with community leaders and primary health officers in developing countries including Nigeria and specifically in the study area and under the free ITN policy, will lead to improved ITN usage and decreased malaria infection and transmission among young children.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Malaria remains a significant public health challenge, particularly affecting children than other group of people. The implementation of the free Insecticide Treated Net (ITN) policy has been a critical strategy in combating malaria and reducing its burden among this age group. Empirical evidence demonstrates that ITNs are highly effective in preventing malaria transmission, reducing morbidity and mortality rates, and improving overall child health outcomes. Findings from various studies confirm that the free ITN policy has led to a significant improvements in ITN ownership, perception and usage, by households with outcome on young children health. Despite these achievements, several barriers such as cultural perception/beliefs lack of proper usage and awareness/knowledge of ITN, and logistical challenges in distribution still hinders the full potential of the policy.

Addressing these barriers through continuous education, community engagement, and improving distribution mechanisms is identified essential to further enhance the effectiveness of ITNs. The free ITN policy has made substantial progress in reducing the burden of malaria among children in Oron. It recommends a continued support targeted interventions and a comprehensive strategies necessary to sustain as well as build on these gains of the policy and ultimately aiming for the eradication of malaria disease in Nigeria. It is therefore believed that implementing the policy plan as recommend will give every child access to and proper use of ITNs to save lives and also contributes to the broader goal of improving public health and socio-economic development of the area and country at large.

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